

Studies on the Dissociation Equilibria in Propan-2-ol + Water Mixtures

D. K. RAM, D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

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The dissociation equilibria for the reactions,

(where, n-phen is 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline) were determined spectrophotometrically in propan-2-ol + water mixtures at 298 K. From the dissociation constant values for the reaction (1), the free energies of transfer of hydrogen ions from water to mixed solvents were calculated. The results were interpreted in terms solute-solvent interactions and solvent basicity.

THE importance of the effects of solutes on the solvent structure, and solute-solvent interactions can be investigated both by the alteration of the solvent composition and the variation of solute structure and charge type. Thus, the introduction of substituents in a ligand may lead to a considerable change in the solute-solvent interactions which may be reflected on the dissociation constants of the ligands and their complexes.

With these objects in view, we have studied the dissociation constants of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline and its tris-complex with Fe^{2+} .

in different propan-2-ol + water mixtures. The study would enable us to have an idea regarding the effects of nitro group on the dissociation constants of the ligand 1,10-phenanthroline and the change in solute-solvent interactions. The results have been presented in this communication.

Experimental

5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline (B.D.H.) was used without further purification. Propan-2-ol (A.R., B.D.H.) was distilled and the middle fraction was utilised within 12 h. Other experimental details are similar to those reported earlier¹⁻⁹.

No report of the diprotonated species of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline is available in literature. In order to ascertain if the diprotonated species be possible for 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline, the absorption spectra of the ligand were run in different acidities (0.001-6 N HClO_4), but found no evidence of the diprotonated species. This is true in the case of 1,10-phenanthroline also. These ligands can not form diprotonated species due to the close proximity of N-atoms which would result in strong proton-proton repulsions in case of diprotonated species. But we found evidence of diprotonated species in case of 2,2'-bipyridine where the following scheme is possible¹⁰.

The $\text{p}K_{\text{BH}^+}$ value of 2,2'-bipyridine is -0.43 (± 0.08) (whereas $\text{p}K(\text{BH}^+)$ is 4.47). Even if we assume the diprotonated species to be possible for 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline, its $\text{p}K_{\text{BH}_2^{2+}}$ value would be expected to be much more negative ($\text{p}K_{\text{BH}^+}$ of 5-nitrophen = 3.23)^{1,3}. Moreover, no values of the Hammett acidity functions are known in mixed solvents. Therefore, under our experimental conditions ($\sim 10^{-2}$ - 10^{-3} M of H^+ ion), no consideration of the diprotonated species is required. Details of spectral studies have been reported elsewhere¹⁰⁻¹², Lee *et al.*¹², Brandt and Gull-

strom¹⁴ and Banks and Bystroff¹⁵ gave no evidence of the presence of the diprotonated species.

Equilibrium studies for the complex between Fe²⁺ and 1,10-phenanthroline, 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridine *etc.* in water have been made by Lee *et al.*^{13,16}, Brandt and Gullstrom¹⁴, Banks and Bystroff¹⁵ and Lahiri *et al.*¹⁻⁹. Lahiri *et al.*²⁻⁹ also made extensive studies in different mixed solvents. It has been found that mono-complexes of Fe²⁺ and 1,10-phenanthroline and its substituted ligands are formed (having a broad absorption in the region 400–460 nm) when excess of Fe²⁺ ion (generally 0.1 M or more) has been added to the ligands (generally of the order of 10⁻⁴ M) in presence of a large excess of acid^{14,16}. Though we determined the stability constant of 1:1 complexes in water, the values can not be regarded to be the thermodynamic values, as the ionic strengths of the solutions were high. Since we are interested in studying the 'medium effects', we prefer not to study the 1:1 complex containing large excess of Fe²⁺ ion and excess of acid in mixed solvents. Moreover, the mono-complex is not stable and is rapidly converted into the tris-complex. This can be well understood if we go through the reports of the kinetics of complex formation between Fe²⁺ ion and 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-dipyridine¹⁷.

$$(k = 5.6 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ at } 298 \text{ K})$$

The second and third step values have not been reported as these steps are too rapid to be measured. [For the bipyridyl ligand also: Fe²⁺ + bipy → $k = 1.6 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$; Febipy²⁺ + bipy → $k = 1.3 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$; the third step is too rapid to be measured]. The most striking feature of the iron complexes of phen (1), substituted-phen, and bipy is that their overall stabilities are abnormally high. The works of Irving and Mellor¹⁸ show conclusively that 'orbital stabilisation' does not take place at the first or second stage but only at the third stage. The values of (log k_2 - log k_3) is very negative implying that the coordination of the third ligand is proceeding with a greater ease in free energy than in the previous two steps. For the reaction,

the electronic rearrangement is manifested in the unusual heat and strong absorption band in the visible spectrum (obviously due to metal to ligand charge transfer at this stage) and by a change in magnetic moments.

It is apparent that the rates of reaction for the steps,

are too rapid to be measured and the complexes are rapidly converted into the tris-form under equilibrium conditions. Thus, under our experimental conditions (with 1:1 or 1:2 ratio of Fe²⁺ ion: n-phen), Fe(n-phen)₃²⁺ is the sole species formed, as observed earlier^{13,15,16,19}. The spectral studies of Fe²⁺ and the ligands in different ratios indicate that the nature of the spectra remains unchanged though the absorbance values change, which indicates only one species under the conditions of the experiment¹¹.

The dissociation constants and the equilibrium constants for the reactions (1-3) have been determined in the way described earlier¹⁻⁹. However, for obtaining the absorbance of the ionic forms, 1-2 M HClO₄ was used as the case may be. The partition technique as used by Irving and Mellor¹⁸ can not be used in mixed solvents. It has been found that in propan-2-ol + water mixtures, generally 12-fold concentration of the ligand is sufficient to bring about the complete complexation of Fe²⁺ ion to Fe(n-phen)₃²⁺. Therefore, the molar absorptivities of nitroferroin were determined from the measurements of the absorbances of solutions containing 12 to 20-fold excess of the ligand to different amounts of Fe²⁺ ion, at 500 and 510 nm (510 nm being the absorption maximum of nitroferroin).

For the determination of the stability constants in propan-2-ol + water mixtures, absorbances of solutions containing different concentrations of Fe²⁺ ion and n-phen were measured at 500 and 510 nm. The H⁺ ion concentrations (calculated) of the solutions ranged 3.0 × 10⁻⁴–3.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, and the ionic strengths of the solution were of the order 2.4 × 10⁻⁴ to 1.4 × 10⁻⁵. Thus, from the absorbance readings and known values of the molar absorptivities, the equilibrium constants for the reaction (2) were determined. The average values have been recorded in Table 1. However, the equilibrium constant for the reaction could not be measured beyond 64.0 wt% of propan-2-ol due to the low solubility of Fe(n-phen)₃(ClO₄)₂ and the consequent precipitation of the complex perchlorate.

Spectrophotometric measurements were taken with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer maintained at 298 K. pH measurements were taken with a Systronic digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit).

Results

Since the reactions are isoelectric in nature and the ionic strengths are low, the concentration equilibrium constants can be regarded to be the thermodynamic constants since $f_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} \approx f_{\text{Fe}(\text{n-phen})_3^{2+}}$ and $f_{\text{H}^+} \approx f_{\text{n-phenH}^+}$. The use of inert electrolytes was carefully avoided as the solute-solvent interactions of unknown magnitude are likely to mask the

TABLE 1—MOLAR ABSORPTION COEFFICIENTS, pK VALUES FOR REACTIONS (1), (2) AND (3) AND FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER OF H⁺ IONS FROM WATER TO PROPAN-2-OL + WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Wt % of 2-PrOH	ϵ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)		pK values for the reactions			$-\Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}(\epsilon)$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		$-\Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ kJ mol ⁻¹
	510 nm	520 nm	(1)	(2)	(3)		(a)	(b)	
0.0	11 785	11 436	3.23						
8.0	12 507	12 140	2.95	5.89	14.74	1.60	0.17	1.14	1.43
16.3	11 333	10 833	2.83	5.64	14.13	2.28	0.41	2.66	1.87
25.1	11 433	10 933	2.36	6.91	13.99	4.96	0.69	3.86	3.27
34.3	10 867	10 333	1.95	7.38	13.23	7.30	1.09	5.12	6.21
43.9	12 333	11 650	1.87	7.10	12.71	7.76	1.59	6.80	6.17
54.0	10 400	10 000	1.63	7.77	12.66	9.12	2.33	8.27	6.79
64.6	8 200	7 506	1.54	8.13	12.75	9.64	3.41	9.94	6.23
75.8			1.43			10.27	4.86	11.47	5.41
87.8			1.60			9.30	6.45	13.42	2.85
93.7			1.64			9.07			

(a) - Calculated using Born equation¹⁹. (b) - Calculated using one-layer model¹⁹.

'medium effects' of ions⁶. We prefer to use very dilute solutions as under our experimental conditions the salt-effect can be eliminated.

The pK_T values for the reaction (1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{p}K_T &= \text{p}C_H + \log \frac{[\text{LH}^+]}{[\text{L}]} \\ &= B + \log U_H \pm \log \frac{d-d_M}{d_1-d} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, L(=n-phen)

The terms have the usual significance as described earlier²⁰⁻²³. The glass electrodes were calibrated and the correction factors log U_H were determined as described earlier²⁰⁻²³. The pC_{H+} values were also calculated from the known amounts of added hydrogen ion. The experimental pH values with corrections have been found to be about +0.02 unit higher than the calculated pC_H values (where C_H⁺ values lie between 10⁻² and 10⁻³, and the concentration of the ligand is of the order of 10⁻⁵M). At higher percentages of propan-2-ol (about 75 wt%), the differences between the experimental and calculated pH values are high, and we have used the calculated values of H⁺ ion concentrations at the higher percentages.

For the determination of the equilibrium constant for the reaction (2),

$$K_a = \frac{C_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} \times C_{\text{LH}^+}}{C_{\text{FeL}_2^+} \times C_{\text{H}^+}} \quad (5)$$

we have,

$$[\text{Fe}^{2+}] = [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{Complex}] \quad (6)$$

$$[\text{LH}^+] = [\text{A}]_{\text{Total}} - 3 [\text{Complex}] - [\text{A}]_{\text{free}} \quad (7)$$

[L]_{free} was calculated from equation (4).

In view of the presence of different ions in the solutions of the complex, which may affect the experimental determination of hydrogen ion concentrations in mixed solvents, we have taken the

values of hydrogen ion concentrations to be given by the known added amounts.

The equilibrium constant for the reaction (3) is given by,

$$K = K_a K_f^2 \quad (8)$$

The results are recorded in Table 1.

Discussion

The pK value of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline passes through a minimum at about 75-80 wt% of propan-2-ol similar to our observations made in the case of 1,10-phenanthroline²⁴. The pK values of n-phen show a linear relationship when plotted against (i) mole fraction, and (ii) 1/ε of the different mixed solvents. Deviations, however, occur at 60 wt% of propan-2-ol. Very little improvement occurs if water activities are taken into consideration²⁵.

The reactions are isoelectric in nature, therefore, the change in dielectric constant should have little effect except for changes in free energy resulting from the differences in the radii of the ions, which, however, can by no means be neglected. But the large changes in pK for the reactions (1-3) must be due to (i) the change in solvent basicity and (ii) the changes in the magnitude of the solute-solvent interactions arising from the differences in solubility of the ligands and their complexes and the differences in the free energy of transfer of ions.

The reaction (1) can be well utilised to calculate the free energy of transfer (or medium effects) of H⁺ ions from water to propan-2-ol + H₂O mixtures, which could throw light on ion-solvent interactions and solvent basicity^{26,27}. The free energy of transfer for the reaction (1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}(1) &= \Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}(\text{n-phen}) + \Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) \\ &\quad - \Delta G_{\ddagger}^{\circ}(\text{n-phen H}^+) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$= \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0(\text{n-phen H}^+) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{since, } \Delta G_i^0(\text{n-phen H}^+) = \Delta G_i^0(\text{n-phen}) + \Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0(\text{n-phen H}^+) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{or, } \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+) = \Delta G_i^0(1) + \Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0(\text{n-phen H}^+) \quad (12)$$

$\Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0$ can be calculated using the simple Born equation²⁸,

$$\Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0 = \frac{166 \times 4.184}{r_{\text{LH}^+}} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_s} - 0.0127 \right) \text{ kJ} \quad (13)$$

or using the one-layer solvation model²⁹,

$$\Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0 = \frac{NZ^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_1} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{b} \right) + \frac{NZ^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_0} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{1}{b} \right) \quad (14)$$

where, a = radius of the bare ion, $b = a + r_s$ (radius of the solvent molecule), $\epsilon_1 = 2$ and ϵ_0 = bulk dielectric constant. The ϵ_0 values have been calculated using the experimental values of Åkerlöf and Short³⁰. $r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $r_{2\text{-PROH}}$ have been taken to be 0.147 and 0.250 nm from the literature³⁰. The radius of 5-n-phenH⁺ has been taken to be equal to 0.37 nm³⁶ (equal to that of 1,10-phenanthroline, calculated).

The differences between $\Delta G_{i(\text{e}i)}^0$ values calculated using Born's equation²⁸ and Abraham's equation²⁹ are quite appreciable. We, however, prefer to use the Born equation. Like all other extra-thermodynamic methods, this method is also not without defect. However, in view of the 'isoelectric' nature of the reaction (1), the effects due to dielectric constants and activity coefficients of the ions are largely eliminated. The $\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$ values calculated by this method are in qualitative agreement with the values reported by us using 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline²⁴ in the same medium. However, quantitatively, the values are more negative (about 0.2 to 1.0 kJ). The introduction of NO₂ group in 1,10-phen changes the extent of solute-solvent interactions considerably, resulting in the differences in $\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$ values. It has been found that $-\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$ is maximum at about 54 wt% of propan-2-ol. This indicates that the basicity is maximum in this region and decreases thereafter.

The molar absorptivities of the complexes were observed to show no systematic variations, and can not be correlated with other data obtained. The observed slight fluctuations are only natural, as the errors involved in the determination of molar absorptivities are usually within 0.4-0.6%. We noted variations in the oscillator strengths of the complexes like ferroin, nitro-ferroin and ferrodiin with change in the solvent systems^{2,10-12}, but any correlation of the oscillator strengths with

solvent properties is not known, and has not been tried.

The results show that the pK_a values for the reaction (2) may show a slight initial decrease with the introduction of organic solvent, but gradually increase thereafter i.e. $\Delta G_i^0(2)$ is positive thereafter. But,

$$\Delta G_i^0(2) = \Delta G_i^0(\text{Fe}^{2+}) + 3 \Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{FeL}_3^{2+}) - 3 \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+) \quad (15)$$

where, L = 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline.

It is seen that $\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$ is increasingly negative. Though $\Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+)$ values are not known, it is expected that the $\Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+)$ should be negative as we get from (9),

$$\Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+) = \Delta G_i^0(\text{L}) + \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_i^0(1) \quad (16)$$

Since the solubility of n-phen is believed to increase in mixed solvents, $\Delta G_i^0(\text{L}) = -2.303 RT \log C_s/C_w$ should be negative. Thus the first and second term of the right hand side of equation (16) are negative, whereas $G_i^0(1)$ is positive, the net result being a negative value of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+)$. The variations of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{Fe}^{2+})$ and $\Delta G_i^0(\text{FeL}_3^{2+})$ with solvent composition is not known. However, it is seen that the stability of the tris-complex of iron(II) gradually diminishes as we go from water to propan-2-ol+water mixtures. This is also evident from the fact that the solubility of the complex decreases enormously beyond 64.0 wt% so as to cause precipitation of the complex.

However, the determination of the solubility products of $\text{Fe}(\text{n-phen})_3(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ and the solubility of 5-nitro-10-phenanthroline could throw more light on the nature of solvation of the complex and the ferrous ion.

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